

Towards an Outcomes-Based Mechanical Engineering Education in the Philippines and the Mapua Institute of Technology School of Mechanical Engineering Experience

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Abstract: The Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering program prescribed by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in its Memorandum Order No. 09 Series of 2008 is designed as outcomes-based. The program outcomes are patterned after the United States Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET) program outcomes. The mechanical engineering program policies, standards and guidelines will be reviewed, revised and enhanced by its respective technical panel of experts in 2011 to reflect outcomes-based education. The goal of the panel is to prepare a curriculum which is ready for international accreditation when the Philippines becomes a member of the Washington Accord.

The paper presents the initiatives and experience of the School of Mechanical Engineering of the Mapua Institute of Technology on outcomes-based education as it recently undergoes the ABET accreditation process and obtains full accreditation. It will discuss some salient point of the accreditation process.

Keywords: outcomes-based, accreditation, CHED, ABET, assessment, evaluation

Introduction

Outcomes-based teaching and learning pertains to a teaching delivery system where the curriculum topics are expressed as the outcomes students are intended to learn. Teaching is designed to directly encourage students to learn those outcomes and that assessment are done to confirm that the students have (City University of Hong Kong). Some of the main points of outcomes-based education include: the identification of outcomes desired by an educational institution to be acquired by its students, the assessment and evaluation of such students to verify the extent of achievement of the outcomes, and a Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI) system in place to ensure that further development of the program is being implemented.

The current trend worldwide is to convert educational instructions from being an input-based, content-centered system to that of an outcomes-based, output-oriented process.

Many institutions in various countries around the world have started exploring and implementing an outcomes-based approach in their educational systems. Some of such countries being referred to include: the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, New Zealand, Hong Kong and now, the Philippines.

CHED Initiatives Towards Outcomes Based Education

The CHED acknowledges the need for Philippine Mechanical Engineering Education to keep abreast with global trends, given the globalized conditions that the world is in. As the world's educational systems gear towards outcomes-based approaches, the CHED has also initiated efforts to structure some higher education programs to be in-line with such trends. Thus, a Memorandum Order (MO) was issued by CHED, which took effect on 10 April 2008, regulating colleges and universities nationwide that offer a degree in mechanical engineering. One key addition to the above-mentioned MO was the requirement

of all colleges and universities concerned to ensure that graduates from their institutions exhibit the attainment of identified Program Outcomes (PO). Such POs included in the MO are based on the minimum ABET requirements for PO attainment of educational institutions offering a degree in mechanical engineering. The POs included in the MO are enumerated below.

Program Outcomes

A graduate of the Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering (BSME) program must have attained:

- a. An ability to apply knowledge of mathematics, science and engineering
- b. An ability to design and conduct experiments, as well as to analyze and interpret data
- c. An ability to design a system, component or process to meet desired needs within realistic constraints
- d. An ability to function on multi-disciplinary teams
- e. An ability to identify, formulate and solve engineering problems
- f. An understanding of professional and ethical responsibility
- g. An ability to communicate effectively in both Filipino and English languages
- h. An understanding of the impact of engineering solutions in a global and societal context
- i. An ability to use techniques, skills and modern engineering tools necessary for mechanical engineering practice

Such initiative by the CHED to gear towards outcomes-based education is subject to revision for further enhancement of the curriculum of the mechanical engineering program in the Philippines. The year 2011 has been set by the Commission's technical panel of experts as a point wherein current policies, standards and guidelines will be reviewed, revised and enhanced. A good source of input for the technical panel will be the experience of the school of mechanical engineering of Mapua Institute of Technology, which has just

recently undergone the first ever international outcomes-based accreditation process of a mechanical engineering program in the Philippines by ABET. One of the end goals of the refinements to be made by the CHED to the provisions included in the MO would be to create policy, standard, and guidelines ready for international accreditation by the time the Philippines becomes a member of the Washington Accord.

Outcomes- Based Accreditation

This section describes the Philippine accreditation processes and agencies and their plan to shift from input-based to outcomes-based accreditation. Outcomes-based accreditation by the Washington Accord and ABET are briefly discussed.

Philippine Accreditation

Assessing the quality of mechanical engineering education in the Philippines is undertaken through the private voluntary accreditation process by an accrediting agency and the peer evaluation process and the periodic review process by the government agency, the Commission on Higher Education Technical Panel for Engineering Technology and Architecture (CHED- TPETA). The professional society and industry participate in the assessment process. The task, therefore, is a multi-sectoral effort of the academia, government, professional society and industry (Belino 2000).

Private voluntary accreditation aims to bring the standards of the educational institutions above the prescribed minimum requirements set by the government. There are four private accrediting agencies in the Philippines under the Federation of Accrediting Agencies of the Philippines (FAAP), namely : Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, College and Universities (PAASCU); the Philippine Association of Colleges and Universities-Commission on Accreditation (PACUCOA); the Association of Christian School and Colleges Accrediting Agency(ACSCAA); and Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and

Universities (AACUP). PAASCU, PACUCOA, and AACUP are three agencies which accredit engineering schools. The federation is created to provide a means for effective coordination, cooperation and sharing of resources. The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) grants administrative deregulation and curricular autonomy to accredited schools based on the level of accreditation given to the school.

However, the accreditation process executed by these accrediting agencies is still input-based. PAASCU and PACUCOA are in the process of going outcomes based.

The Washington Accord

It is not enough for Philippine educational institutions to be complacent with being accredited by local accreditation bodies, as such may result in a situation wherein the Philippine education system may drastically fall behind its global neighbors, in the globalized economy we are in. To avoid this, CHED aims to be included in the membership of international education alliances, specifically the Washington Accord.

According to its website (<http://www.washingtonaccord.org>), the Washington Accord, signed in 1989, is an international agreement among bodies responsible for accrediting engineering degree programs. It recognizes the substantial equivalency of programs accredited by those bodies and recommends that graduates of programs accredited by any of the signatory bodies be recognized by the other bodies as having met the academic requirements for entry to the practice of engineering. So far, many countries have already become signatories to the agreement. In Asia, nations that have joined the alliance include: Chinese Taipei, Hong Kong, Japan, Korea, Malaysia and Singapore. India, Pakistan, Russia, Sri Lanka and Turkey currently hold a provisional status.

ABET Accreditation

ABET, Inc. is recognized by the Council for Higher Education Accreditation, and is also among the most respected accreditation organizations in the United States for college and university programs in applied science, computing, engineering, and technology, composed of 28 professional and technical societies representing such fields. ABET accredits more than 2,700 programs at over 550 colleges and universities in the United States alone, not including non-U.S. educational institutions (<http://www.abet.org>).

Mapua Institute of Technology Experience

In line with both the mission and vision of the Institute to be a global center of excellence in education and the national initiative to further improve educational programs in the country, the Mapua Institute of Technology has taken the leap and the lead in the country towards international accreditation of its programs. Three programs offered by the Institute have already been accredited by ABET, which include: Electrical Engineering; Electronics and Communications Engineering; and, Computer Engineering. During the latter part of 2010, other programs of Mapua Institute of Technology have undergone the ABET accreditation process as well. Such programs include: Chemical Engineering, Civil Engineering, Environmental and Sanitary Engineering, Industrial Engineering, Mechanical Engineering, Computer Science and Information Technology.

Having several programs accredited by ABET, the Institute has reached a level in which it is much more confident and capable in providing world-class education to its students. The Institute has started sharing its experience to other colleges and universities in the Philippines if ever they decide to go through international accreditation of their programs on top of their local accreditation. Mapua Institute of Technology has partnered with the PACUCOA to share experiences and knowledge to shift to outcomes-based education and accreditation.

The School of Mechanical Engineering

In line with the Institute's commitment of continually moving forward towards attaining a world-class quality, outcomes-based education, the School of Mechanical Engineering has drafted its new vision-mission depicted in the vision board below.

Figure 1. ME Vision Board (2010- 2020)

The gear is driven by the pinion which is the vision-mission of the School. The three areas of a world-class education inscribed in the gear are outcomes-based and learner-centered instruction; high-impact and cutting-edge research; and, relevant and meaningful extension service. These areas are dynamic, changing, and improving as they always interact and relate with external linkages such as industry, professional societies, and other academic institutions.

In preparation for the ABET accreditation visit, the School reported its best features in the areas of instruction, students, laboratory facilities, research and publication, community extension service, and industry-academe linkages. However, research and publication and extension service are not included in the ABET nine criteria which are students, program educational objectives, program outcomes, continuous improvement,

curriculum, faculty, facilities, support and program criteria.

Instruction. The School designed and implemented an innovative curriculum with tracks in mechatronics, automotive and HVAC/R engineering. Other features include a full blown undergraduate thesis project, a local and international on-the-job training program, and a capstone design project as the culminating design experience taking into account multiple constraints and local and international technical codes and standards. To give the students more hands-on experience and depth in the teaching of the courses in the different tracks, partnerships with industry and professional societies such as Toyota Philippines, Cummins Diesel Engines, Pilipinas Shell, Concepcion-Carrier, Philippine Society of Ventilating, Air-conditioning and Refrigeration Engineers (PSVARE) and American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) Philippine Chapter were forged. Academic linkages with Chung Yuan Christian University in Taiwan and Sungkyunkwan University in South Korea were also established to enhance the mechatronics concentration.

Faculty. There was substantial improvement in the faculty academic qualification. Four members of the faculty are recognized academicians; national outstanding teacher/international awardee as faculty adviser; nationally acclaimed mathematician; and, local and international science and technology journal editor. Four members of the faculty are pursuing their PhD in mechanical engineering. Part-time faculty are outstanding industry practitioners. Faculty attendance to international conferences such as ASHRAE Chapter Regional Conference, ASHRAE Winter Meeting, American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) Mechanical Engineering Education Conference, American Society for Engineering Education (ASEE) Global Colloquium in Engineering Education and Association for Engineering Education in Southeast Asia and the Pacific (AESEAP) Engineering Education Conference has

become very evident. A number of these faculty have assumed leadership roles in local and international professional societies such as the Philippine Society of Mechanical Engineers (PSME), Philippine Institute of Mechanical Engineering Educators (PIMEE), ASHRAE and AEESEAP.

Students. Student chapters of local and international professional societies such as PSME, PIMEE, ASHRAE, ASME and SME have been established. Some of these chapters have received awards and grants which included: ASME Diversity Grant; ASHRAE Undergraduate Senior Project Grant; ASHRAE Student Achievement Award; and, ASHRAE Student Advisor/Branch of the Year Award.

Through these organizations, the students have attended conferences in Taiwan, Thailand, Singapore and the United States. Just recently, a team of students joined the First Shell Eco-Marathon in Asia and won ninth place among 47 entries in the proto-type gasoline engine category and first runner-up in safety award. Two more professional societies such as Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) and ASEE are in the pipeline for establishment. Special interest group such as Robotics Hobby Club in the School is open for membership not only to mechanical engineering students but also to others considering its multidisciplinary nature.

Facilities. The laboratory facilities of the School is one of the best in the country. The minimum requirements of the Commission on Higher Education for teaching laboratories have been exceeded with new acquisitions to supplement the three tracks in mechatronics, automotive, and HVAC/R engineering. Donated equipment from Toyota Philippines and Cummins Diesel Engines further enhanced the automotive engineering laboratory.

Research and Publication. High impact research undertakings in the fields of renewable energy ,automotive engineering, HVAC/R and engineering education have been undertaken. Faculty members published in

local and international journals and won in national and international research competition.

Extension Service and Linkages. Highly relevant and meaningful community extension projects equivalent to U.S. “Engineers Without Borders” projects which prioritized uplifting of the social conditions of the poor in the rural area have been done. New and strengthened industry linkages were forged with Toyota, Hitachi, Shell, Sunpower, Cummins, Carrier and other companies. Academic linkages with Asian and American universities were formed for student and faculty exchange and collaborative research.

Learning and Insights Before and After ABET Accreditation Visit

After the receipt and acknowledgement by ABET of the application sent by the Institute, ABET requires the submission of a Self Study Report (SSR) per program to be evaluated. The SSR contains various information that the visiting ABET team of evaluators will need to initially verify whether the program may be fit for an accreditation visit. The SSR generally includes the following main areas of the educational program requesting for accreditation: information on students of the program, assessment and evaluation of both the Program Educational Objectives (PEO) and the Program Outcomes (PO), Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI) process, curriculum, faculty, facilities and support.

CQI. Undertaking international accreditation built around continuous improvement is a big leap for the Institute committed to provide world-class education to its student. Such an endeavor requires careful and well-thought planning and full support from the various constituencies such as the administration, faculty, students, support staff and alumni.

These various constituencies should have a clear understanding of the definitions of important terms like program educational

objectives, program outcomes, assessment, evaluation and continuous quality improvement.

Assessment. One of the major insights brought about by the accreditation process undergone by the School was in the manner assessments were done. Assessment corresponds to the process of obtaining data, which can be used for the purpose of measuring achievement (Rogers 2002).

The School acquired a lot of useful and very practical knowledge regarding the conduct of assessment. The relevance of assessment can not be underestimated, since it is the primary tool of an Institute to determine the degree to which the mission and vision of the school has been attained. Such levels of attainment may be reflected upon by the level of satisfying the set PEOs and POs. Assessment plays a very critical role in outcomes-based education.

To avoid collecting tons of student portfolios, the faculty of a course cluster teaching a certain course must agree on the assessment method of the identified program outcomes. G. Rogers of Rose-Hulman Institute of Technology advises that assessment of program outcomes must not be based on the final grades which are a composite of different outcomes

It is practical to identify a course topic in assessing a particular program outcome. Assessing too many if not all program outcomes in a course may lead to “death by assessment” according to R. Warder of the University of Memphis. More data are not necessarily better.

Evaluation. After the conduct of assessments, the School then proceeds with analyzing the data gathered. Rogers (2002) defined evaluation as the process of utilizing data gathered from assessment to know the value of the data obtained and provide information for future actions to be taken.

Faculty members of the School, who are critical to the flawless execution of OBE

processes, regularly meet to evaluate data gathered from assessment tools used in courses and for obtaining inputs from other constituents. The results of the evaluation are then used to identify aspects in the program that need to be improved on.

The topics of assessment and evaluation are very wide in its scope and are not going to be tackled in detail in this paper.

Final remarks

Given limited time and resources, one cannot do all. Thus, it is very important to plan and think thoroughly about the whole accreditation process. However, there is no such thing as a “perfect” plan. The entire accreditation process is a learning experience for the administration, faculty and support staff.

While getting accredited that enhances the reputation and image of the school is very important, learning from the entire process and improving certain practices to deliver a much better quality of education to our students should be the main goal. Accreditation should open also new opportunities to students in terms of scholarships and their future employment and career path.

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